

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Rices with multiple disease resistance

V. P. S. Dev and C. A. Mary, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Pattambi 679306, Kerala, India

In 1983 kharif, under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 328 rice cultures of National Screening Nursery I were evaluated at RARS for resistance to blast (BL), sheath blight (ShB), and bacterial blight (BB). B1 screening was done under upland condi-

tions using the uniform B1 nursery pattern. Screening for ShB and BB was in transplanted fields with artificially induced disease. Each test entry was planted in two 2-m rows spaced at 20 × 15 cm for ShB and BB in 2 separate plots. Disease reactions were judged using the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale*.

Sixteen entries were resistant to both B1 and ShB, 6 entries to B1 and BB, and 39 entries to ShB and BB. Four entries had resistance to the three diseases (see table). □

Rices with multiple resistance to B1, ShB, and BB, RARS, Pattambi, India.

IET no.	Cross	Reaction ^a to		
		BL	ShB	BB
8236	CR-151-79/CR1014	MR	MR	R
8288	Vikram/Benong III	MR	MR	MR
8314	IR32/IET6314	MR	MR	MR
8748	Jaya/T22A	R	R	MR

^a MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant.

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INSECT RESISTANCE

Virulence of green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* colonies on rice cultivars with the *Glh 2* or *Glh 5* gene for resistance

E. A. Heinrichs and H. R. Rapusas, IRRI

We have unsuccessfully attempted to select GLH colonies that are virulent on ASD7 (which has the *Glh 2* gene for resistance) and on ASD8 (with *Glh 5*). We sought to determine whether other colonies selected for 37 generations for

virulence to Pankhari 203 (*Glh 1*), IR8 (*Glh 3*), Ptb 8 (*glh 4*), TAPL #796 (*Glh 6*), and Moddai Karuppan (*Glh 7*) had cross virulence to ASD7 or ASD8.

Results were compared with colonies reared on susceptible TN1. Resistance scoring was based on population growth.

Six-day-old seedlings of the test cultivars were transplanted, 5 seedlings/pot, in 10-cm-diam clay pots. There were four replications, with each pot representing a replication. Two weeks after transplanting, the individual pots were placed

in 10- × 90-cm mylar film cages to protect them from other pests, parasites, and predators. Ten days later, they were inspected and all parasites, predators, and other pests were removed from the cage. Then, 5 pair (male and female) of GLH adults from the different colonies were introduced into each cage. Twenty-five days after infestation, the GLH population in each cage was counted and progeny per female was calculated.

There were significant differences in the levels of resistance among the seven

Population growth of GLH on different rice cultivars, IRRI.

Cultivar	Gene	Population growth (progeny/female) on each colony ^a											
		Pankhari 203		IR8		Ptb 8		TAPL 796		Moddai Karuppan		TN1	
ASD7	<i>Glh 2</i>	1 a	(a)	1 a	(a)	1 a	(a)	1 a	(a)	1 a	(a)	4 a	(a)
Godalki	<i>Glh 2</i>	120	d(a)	55	c (a)	76	d (a)	84	d (a)	68	de (a)	82	d (a)
Lien-tsan 50	<i>Glh 2</i>	27	cd (c)	3 a	(a)	4 b	(a)	8	bcd (ab)	11	c (ab)	19	b (bc)
Palasithari 601	<i>Glh 2</i>	7	c (a)	3 a	(a)	10	bc (a)	2	bc (a)	11	cd (a)	9	ab (a)
Ernest	<i>Glh 2</i>	10	c (ab)	1 a	(a)	10	bc (b)	5	bcd (ab)	5	b (ab)	19	b (b)
Bignou	<i>Glh 2</i>	33	cd (b)	14	ab (ab)	16	bc (ab)	11	cd (a)	32	cde (b)	26	bc (ab)
Tilockkachari	<i>Glh 2</i>	1	b (a)	1 a	(a)	1 a	(a)	2	b (a)	1 a	(a)	3	a (a)
ASD8	<i>Glh 5</i>	4	c (ab)	1 a	(a)	3	b (a)	1	a (a)	2	ab (a)	20	b (b)
IR29 (resistant check)	Unidentified	23	cd (ab)	22	bc (ab)	25	cd (ab)	3	b (a)	75	de (c)	51	cd (b)
TN1 (susceptible check)	None	134	d (a)	75	d (a)	76	d (a)	97	d (a)	135	e (a)	63	d (a)

^aAv of 4 replications in a column or in a row (in parentheses), means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

cultivars with the *Glh 2* gene (see table). ASD7 and Tilockkachari were highly resistant to all GLH colonies, indicating no cross virulence of the colonies to those two varieties. Population growth on

Godalki was similar to that on susceptible TN1 for all colonies. ASD8 was highly resistant to all colonies. The Moddai Karuppan colonies were more virulent on IR29 than the other colonies. The

study indicated that none of the colonies selected on the various resistant cultivars were more suitable than the TN1 colony as a source of insects to begin a selection program on ASD7 or ASD8. □

Reaction to *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley of varieties resistant to *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guené

R. C. Joshi, E. Medina, and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

Leaffolders *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* are almost identical in external appearance and have recently caused similar damage in rice fields in Laguna, Philippines. We evaluated 30 rice varieties previously identified as highly susceptible or moderately resistant to *C. medinalis* for their reaction to *M. patnalis*.

First-instar larvae at 2 larvae/tiller were caged on 36-d-old rice plants kept in the greenhouse. Each accession was replicated six times and treatments were in a split-plot design with the leaffolder species as the main plot and rice varieties subplots. The 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice* was used to score damage.

Damage from the two species was not significantly different at the 5% level. Damage ratings were correlated ($P > 0.05$). Varietal differences within a leaffolder species occurred (see table). Susceptible TN1, commonly used to screen varieties for *C. medinalis* resistance also can be used as a susceptible check for *M. patnalis*. Ptb 33, ASD5, TKM6, IR4707-106-3-2, Darukasail, and GEB24 are possible donors for resistance to the two leaffolder species. □

Reactions of rice varieties to *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis*, IRRI, 1984.

Variety	Accession no.	Origin	Leaf damage ^a					
			<i>C. medinalis</i>		<i>M. patnalis</i>			
			Damage rating (%)	Scale	Damage rating (%)	Scale		
TN1	105	Taiwan	27.3	d	—	25.5	f	—
ARC6650	12308	India	22.0	cd	9	22.4	ef	9
IR36	1187	Philippines	21.0	cd	9	22.3	ef	9
Shete	46671	India	21.1	cd	9	20.1	def	9
ARC5752	12119	India	20.6	cd	9	19.1	cdef	9
ARC10560	20992	India	19.8	cd	7	19.8	def	9
ARC10550	12507	India	19.7	cd	7	19.0	cdef	7
BKN-BR1008-21	—	Thailand	22.0	cd	9	15.1	bcdef	7
Khao-rad	48069	Thailand	17.4	abc	7	19.2	cdef	7
Balam	49020	Bangladesh	16.0	abc	7	19.6	def	9
Calixto	47166	Philippines	21.8	cd	9	13.6	bcdef	7
Khao-Ma Khaek	47852	Thailand	18.1	abc	7	17.0	cde	7
IR5685-26-1	39433	Philippines	19.0	bcd	7	15.5	bcdef	7
Gorsa	49088	Bangladesh	16.3	abc	7	17.8	cde	7
Karpur Kanti	46048	India	15.6	abc	7	17.9	cde	7
Bora	49157	Bangladesh	16.3	abc	7	15.2	bcdef	7
Biron	49154	Bangladesh	17.7	abc	7	13.5	bcdef	7
Yakadayan	36408	Sri Lanka	17.1	abc	7	13.3	bcdef	7
Muthumanikam	15327	Sri Lanka	18.1	abc	7	12.3	abcd	5
Vashaipoo Samba	—	India	14.8	abc	7	13.8	bcdef	7
CO 7	6041	India	12.9	abc	5	15.2	bcdef	7
ASD7	6303	India	16.5	abc	7	11.6	abcd	5
Kataribhog	46076	India	14.3	abc	7	12.9	abcde	7
W 1263	11657	India	15.9	abc	7	10.7	abcd	5
Ptb 33	19325	India	12.9	abc	5	13.3	bcdef	7
ASD5	5812	India	13.4	abc	5	11.6	abc	5
TKM6	237	India	13.3	abc	5	10.1	abc	5
IR4707-106-3-2	47459	Philippines	9.6	a	5	13.4	bcdef	7
Darukasail	45493	India	14.9	abc	7	7.9	a	5
GEB24	5909	India	9.7	ab	5	8.7	ab	5
Mean			17.2			15.6		

^aAv of 6 replications. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Testing for field resistance in rice under induced brown planthopper (BPH) outbreaks

P. S. Prakasa Rao, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack 753006, India

From several years of research at CRRI, we have developed a reliable field method for inducing BPH hopperburn. This is helping us to identify promising field-resistant rices. The following steps ensure

heavy BPH incidence.

- Two erect wind-breaker walls made of glass fiber-based bitumen felt or local bamboo mat (0.75 m high around test entries and 1.5 m high, around tall, long-duration varieties) are installed. They withstand high winds and keep the experimental area undisturbed by wind (Fig. 1).
- Three to five cm of standing water is maintained in treated plots.
- A lush rice canopy is maintained by

applying up to 25 kg N/ha in convenient splits until 60 d after planting (DAP).

- Insect colonies are established by confining BPH for 24 h in cylindrical 50- × 15-cm fine wire mesh cages (Fig. 1).
- Progressive BPH colonization is provided between 10 and 60 DAP to reach 1 adult BPH/hill.
- Rice is transplanted at 10- × 10-cm spacing in two 1.5-m-long rows per